

Reactions of the Cobaltic Ion.
Part III: Kinetics of the Silver-catalysed Reduction of
Cobalt (III) with Acetic Acid

J. K. Sthapak* and S. Ghosh

Silver (I) is a much used catalyst in the oxidation of many inorganic ions^{1,2}. In addition, many persulphate³⁻⁶ oxidations are accelerated by the presence of silver (I) due to the formation of silver (II) or silver (III). However, it is only recently that a few silver-catalysed cobalt (III) oxidations of some inorganic ions^{7,8} have been investigated. It is also known that the reduction of cobalt (III) in aqueous sulphuric acid with acetic⁹ and acrylic acids is very slow at low temperatures ($\approx 20^\circ$). It has, therefore, been thought of to study the silver-catalysed reduction of cobalt (III) with acetic and acrylic acids¹⁰. In the present paper kinetic studies of the silver-catalysed reduction of cobalt (III) with acetic acid have been presented.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The experimental procedure is similar to that as has been described in an earlier communication¹¹. The loss of cobalt (III) is estimated iodometrically. It may be stated here that silver (I) does not interfere in the estimation of the oxidant as its minute concentrations have been used. The concentration of acetic acid is always in excess than that of cobalt (III) or silver (I).

* Present Address : Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, Government Engineering College, Jabalpur, M.P., India.

1. W. C. E. Higginson, D. R. Rosseinsky, J. B. Stead and A. G. Sykes, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, **29**, 49-59.
2. J. B. Stead, Thesis Manchester University, 1959.
3. D. M. Yost, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 152; *ibid.*, 1926, **48**, 374.
4. D. D. Mishra and S. Ghosh, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41** (VI), 397-406.
5. D. D. Mishra and S. Ghosh, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, 1964, **34** (II), 317-21.
6. D. D. Mishra and S. Ghosh, *Proc. Natl. Instt. Sci.*, 1965, **31** (A-II), 119-25.
7. J. B. Kirwin, P. J. Proll and L. H. Sutcliffe, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, **40**, 119-26.
8. J. B. Kirwin, F. D. Peat, P. J. Proll and L. H. Sutcliffe, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 1617; *ibid.*, 1963, **67**, 2288.
9. J. K. Sthapak and S. Ghosh, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.* (Communicated).
10. J. K. Sthapak and S. Ghosh, Unpublished work.
11. J. K. Sthapak and S. Ghosh, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.* (Communicated).

The effect of different concentrations of silver (I), sulphuric, and acetic acids on the rate of reduction of cobalt (III) at different temperatures has been studied and average values of the observed first order rate constants have been incorporated in the following table. The results have been found to be reproducible with a maximum deviation of $\pm 5\%$.

TABLE

Cobalt (III) initial = $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ K-salts of $H_2SO_4 = 0.25 N$

No.	Acetic Acid Conc. (M)	Sulphuric Acid Conc. (M)	Silver (I) Conc. (M)	Temp. (± 0.1)	K_1 obs. $\times 10^3$ min $^{-1}$
1.	1.00	2.875	1.56×10^{-5}	25	17.39
2.	1.00	2.875	-do-	30	34.98
3.	1.00	2.875	3.12×10^{-5}	25	24.46
4.	1.00	2.875	-do-	30	49.10
5.	1.00	3.875	1.56×10^{-5}	25	17.69
6.	1.00	3.875	-do-	30	44.68
7.	1.00	3.875	3.12×10^{-5}	25	27.68
8.	1.00	3.875	-do-	30	50.71
9.	2.00	2.875	1.56×10^{-5}	25	17.69
10.	2.00	2.875	-do-	30	43.41
11.	2.00	2.875	3.12×10^{-5}	25	26.46
12.	2.00	2.875	-do-	30	56.38
13.	2.00	3.875	1.56×10^{-5}	25	21.88
14.	2.00	3.875	-do-	30	45.21
15.	2.00	3.875	3.12×10^{-5}	25	30.44
16.	2.00	3.875	-do-	30	60.80
17.	3.00	2.875	1.56×10^{-5}	25	19.14
18.	3.00	2.875	3.12×10^{-5}	25	27.29
19.	3.00	3.875	1.56×10^{-5}	25	26.07
20.	3.00	3.875	3.12×10^{-5}	25	32.06

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before discussing the mechanism of this reaction, it is essential to summarise the conclusions drawn from the reaction between cobalt (III) and silver (I) in perchloric acid and also from the reaction of cobalt (III) with acetic acid in aqueous sulphuric acid. It has been reported that in the reaction of cobalt (III) with silver (I) in perchloric acid an equilibrium producing silver (II) and cobalt (II) is readily set up⁸ and at 25° a value of 0.76 for an ionic

strength of 2.5 *M* has been assigned to the equilibrium constant. The rate of disappearance of cobalt (III) is reported to be of second order. We have also observed (table omitted) that the rate of decomposition of cobalt (III) in presence of silver (I) in aqueous sulphuric acid is of second order.

In the case of uncatalysed reaction between cobalt (III) and acetic acid in aqueous sulphuric acid under similar conditions, the order with respect to both cobalt (III) and acetic acid is one and the effect of sulphuric acid is to enhance the reduction of cobalt (III); whereas in all the cases where silver (I) has been used as a catalyst, the reaction is of first order with respect to cobalt (III) and of fractional or zero order but slightly positive for acetic acid. The effect of sulphuric acid is to enhance the reaction rate slightly. The total order of reaction irrespective of the concentration of silver (I) and sulphuric acid is, therefore, one. From what has been noted, it is clear that a different mechanism is operating in the silver (I) catalysed reaction of cobalt (III) with acetic acid.

It has been reported by Ying Peh Tong and King¹² that rate of reaction between chromium (III) and cerium (IV) in perchloric acid solution is too rapid to be measured by simple techniques. By the addition of a ligand like SO_4^{--} anion, which exchanges slowly and reduces the reactivity of cerium (IV) considerably, it has been possible for them to retard the reaction sufficiently for a full kinetic investigation.

By a similar analogy, in contrast to the observations of Sutcliffe *et al.*, who have reported a rapid establishment of equilibrium in the reaction between cobalt (III) + silver (I) in perchloric acid, we may suggest here the reaction (i) to be slow and rate-determining. Thus :

Silver (II) may also be formed via the equilibrium :

But its concentration will be very small¹⁴.

As the reaction (i) is slow, it will demand the first order dependence of the reaction rate on silver (I) also, which has not been observed as noted for acrylic acid at lower temperatures. The departure may be due to the auto-decomposition of higher valency state silver in acidic solutions at higher temperatures. An increase in the concentration of sulphuric acid from 2.875 to 3.875 *M* enhances the reaction rate slightly.

The effect on the rate is most likely to be combination of specific complexes of silver (II) or cobalt (III) and on ionic strength variation as both the decomposition of silver (II) and the cobalt (III) + Ag (I) reaction have their rates affected by variation of the perchloric acid and the perchlorate ion concentrations. A similar catalytic effect by SO_4^{--} anions

12. J. Ying-Peh Tong and E. L. King, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 3805.

13. K. G. Ashurst and W. C. E. Higginson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **70**, 343-49.

14. A. A. Noyes, C. D. Coryell, F. Stitt and A. Kossiakoff, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 1316.

has been observed by Higginson and co-workers¹³ for cobalt (III) and thallium (I) reaction in perchloric acid. Our studies, however, are very limited for a definite conclusion to be arrived at.

In the present investigation, the concentration of acetic acid has always been greater than that of cobalt (III) or silver (I). We have also noted that acetic acid evolves carbon-dioxide when heated with persulphate in presence of silver (I). Again, the concentration of Ag (III) is much lower than that of Ag (II) and as the order of reaction of acetic acid is almost zero, the next step may be written as

An average value of the energy of activation for uncatalysed reaction is 37.00 k.cal.mole⁻¹; whereas it is only 28.6 k.cal.mole⁻¹ for the catalysed reaction. The associated entropies of activation for the two reactions are +45.94 e.u. and +55.32 e.u., respectively. The reaction, therefore, becomes more feasible in presence of silver (I) due to a decrease in the value of energy of activation and an increase in entropy of activation. The large positive value of entropy of activation is probably a consequence of working with reaction mixtures of high ionic strengths.

One of the authors (J.K.S.) is thankful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the award of a research fellowship.

Department of Postgraduate Studies
and Research in Chemistry,
Jabalpur University,
Jabalpur.

*Received October 24, 1968,
Revised MSS received July 10, 1969.*